

Displacement tuning in a human cochlear model

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Abstract. The displacement of structures within the human cochlea cannot be measured directly but may be inferred from indirect measurements of cochlear outputs. Two essential signal-processing features of the cochlea are minimum audible pressure (MAP) (Killion 1978) and forward latency (FL) (Neely et al. 1988). While a one-dimensional (1D) transmission-line model of cochlear mechanics is ideal for computational efficiency, attempts to achieve both MAP and FL in the same model have been unsuccessful. To overcome the limitations of the 1D model without sacrificing computational efficiency, a new type of cochlear model is introduced that represents three-fluid chambers (3FC): scala tympani (ST), scala vestibuli (SV), and spiral sulcus (SS). The inclusion of the SS as a third fluid chamber breaks SV-ST symmetry and represents interaction of the sensory-cell hair bundles (HB) with SS fluid that is independent of basilar membrane (BM) motion. The 3FC model comes closer than the 1D model to achieving MAP and FL targets and allows comparison of HB tuning with BM tuning.

INTRODUCTION

In the absence of direct measurements of structural motion in a normally functioning human cochlea, which may differ from those in animal models, cochlear models must rely on indirect measurements for guidance. These include (1) sound pressures of minimum audible tones, (2) latencies of auditory brainstem response (ABR), and (3) various psychoacoustic measures. In Fig. 1, forward latency is defined by subtracting 5 ms from the tone-burst ABR Wave V latency. The subtraction accounts for synaptic and neural delays between the cochlea and the cochlear nucleus (Neely et al. 1988). The remaining delay, (i.e., forward latency) must be primarily due to cochlear mechanics. Note in Fig. 1 that forward latency decreases as sound level increases and that the rate of decrease is about the same across a wide range of frequencies. Lines fitted to the data were observed to have slopes of -18 dB/octave. This trend has been modeled (Neely and Rasetshwane, 2017) by introducing nonlinearity into outer hair cell (OHC) transduction, which reduces OHC motility for high-level sounds, thereby broadening basilar-membrane (BM) tuning.

COCHLEAR MODEL

A multi-chamber cochlear model represents fluid mechanics in terms of coupled longitudinal and radial motion. The radial cross-section in Fig. 2 represents four incompressible fluid-filled chambers: (1) scala vestibuli (SV), (2) scala tympani (ST), (3) spiral sulcus (SS), and (4) the fluid space below the reticular lamina in the organ of Corti (OC). Let $\mathbf{U}_\ell(x_n)$ represent longitudinal volume velocity and $\mathbf{U}_r(x_n)$ represent radial volume velocity in each chamber at locations $x_n = n\Delta_x$ uniformly distributed along the longitudinal dimension from base to apex. If the length of the cochlea is L , then $x_N = L$ and $\Delta_x = L/N$. Fluid volume conservation require the radial velocity at each location to equal the difference between adjacent longitudinal velocities:

$$\mathbf{U}_r(x_n) = \mathbf{U}_\ell(x_n) - \mathbf{U}_\ell(x_{n+1}), \quad (1)$$

for $n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$. Boundary conditions are imposed at the base and apex. At the base, $\mathbf{U}_\ell(x_0)$ represents the volume velocity of the oval and round windows, which should sum to zero to conserve fluid volume. At the apex, also known as the helicotrema, $\mathbf{U}_\ell(x_N)$ is zero in each chamber due to fluid coupling.

Longitudinal fluid acceleration $\dot{\mathbf{U}}_\ell(x_n)$ is related to fluid pressure $\mathbf{P}(x_n)$ by a finite-difference equation of motion:

$$\dot{\mathbf{U}}_\ell(x_n) = \frac{A(x_n)}{\rho \Delta x} [\mathbf{P}(x_{n-1}) - \mathbf{P}(x_n)], \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{A} represent the fluid pressure and cross-sectional area of each chamber, respectively. The radial flow at each longitudinal location $\mathbf{U}_r(x_n)$ is additionally constrained by micromechanics.

Figure 1. ABR forward latency (adapted from Neely et al. 1988). The symbols represent average cochlear latencies based on toneburst ABR measurements in human adults.

Figure 2. Schematic of a cochlear radial cross-section showing four fluid chambers (SV, ST, SS, OC) separated by anatomical partitions (BM, tectorial membrane (TM), reticular lamina (RL)).

Historically, non-uniform transmission lines have been useful models of cochlear mechanics. A transmission-line model is essentially a two-chamber model (SV+ST) with an additional symmetry constraint imposed between the two chambers. A two-chamber model allows only a single degree-of-freedom (DOF) in the cross-section radial motion. In this paper, we consider the effect on cochlear micromechanics of a second radial DOF by including the longitudinal flow of a third fluid chamber, the SS.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Time-domain models of cochlear mechanics are required for accurately simulating level-dependent features. Since our three-chamber model is not yet fully implemented in the time-domain, we first present the level-dependent features of a two-chamber, time-domain model. Subsequently, we use frequency-domain models to illustrate differences in tuning curves between models with two and three chambers. In both the time-domain and frequency-domain implementations, simple models of a sound transducer, ear canal, and middle-ear are prepended to the cochlear model to allow the specification of stimuli as voltage waveforms.

Level Dependence of Forward Latency and Forward Masking

Hair-bundle displacement is transformed to neural-spike rate by a simple model of the inner-hair-cell (IHC) transduction and afferent synapse. Spike rates summed across the entire length of the cochlea are used as a whole-nerve response (WNR). Forward latency, as shown in Fig. 3 and is modeled as the time-delay of the WNR peak. Its level dependence is due to a combination of nonlinear OHC transduction and nonlinear synaptic adaptation, which is modeled as a single-reservoir diffusion process (Neely and Rasetshwane, 2017).

The amplitude of the WNR peak is reduced by the presence of a preceding tone. In the model, this peak-amplitude reduction is due to synaptic adaptation. In psychoacoustics, this phenomenon is known as forward masking. An example of the dependence of forward masking on masker level is shown in Fig. 4, which compares psychoacoustic measurements with model results.

Figure 3. WNR latency in a non-linear, active, time-domain cochlear model shows a similar dependence on stimulus frequency and level as forward latency (see Fig. 1).

Figure 4. Amount of tone-on-tone forward masking at 1 kHz for three masker-tone levels and three probe-tone delays measured by Jesteadt et al. (1982) modeled by WNR.

Simultaneous comparison between model results and psychoacoustic measurements of forward latency and forward masking places complementary constraints on the relative contributions of OHC transduction and synaptic adaptation to the simulation of these level-dependent features in the model.

Ensemble Averaging and Loudness

Loudness is the perceptual correlate of the physical intensity of a sound. However, loudness also varies with the bandwidth of a sound in a manner that is difficult to predict from cochlear mechanics alone. The phenomenon of increasing loudness with increasing bandwidth is known in psychoacoustics as *loudness summation*. We have used the two-chamber cochlear model described above to explore the idea that loudness summation is due to ensemble averaging across subsets of auditory nerve fibers, which produces frequency-specific partial-loudness estimates in the cochlear nucleus.

The cochlear model (described above) represents the length of the cochlea (from base to apex) by points at $N_x = 1401$ discrete locations. The IHC at each location generates a time-varying neural rate. We calculate a set of ensemble neural rates by taking root-mean-square (RMS) averages across the single-point neural rates within longitudinal spans of the cochlea defined by an ensemble width in millimeters (mm). Each ensemble neural rate is converted to a partial loudness by a nonlinear transformation that replicates the growth of the loudness of tones (Rasetshwane et al., 2015), as shown in Fig. 5. The two model parameters that describe the ensemble-averaging process are (1) the number of ensembles N_e and (2) the ensemble width W_e .

Figure 5. The growth of loudness with stimulus level (left panel), was measured for tones by Rasetshwane et al. (2015). The growth of loudness with stimulus bandwidth (right panel), known as loudness summation, is replicated in the model and shows similarity to the measured loudness summation of Liebold et al. (2007).

Our preliminary comparisons of the cochlear model with the loudness-summation measurements of Leibold et al. (2007) (see Fig. 5) suggest that the best agreement is achieved when the number of ensembles and ensemble width are $N_e = 140$ and $W_e = 3$ mm, respectively. The specific parameter values are less important than the idea that loudness summation may provide evidence of neural ensemble averaging. Specific details of the ensemble-averaging implementation are expected to evolve as more comprehensive loudness-summation estimates become available.

Additionally, spectrographic analysis of speech based on Fourier Transforms (see Fig. 6) has notable similarities and difference when compared to speech perception in terms of partial loudness, as shown in Fig. 7. In this context, we define partial loudness as the contribution to the total loudness perception originating from a subset (or ensemble) of auditory nerve fibers.

Figure 6. Waveform and spectrogram of /aba/. Fourier-transform frequencies have been mapped to their characteristic place in the cochlea. This spectrogram required a computation time of less than 1 second.

Figure 7. Perceptogram of /aba/. Partial loudness results from neural-ensemble averaging. This perceptogram required a computation time of almost one hour (3408 seconds).

One way that the perceptogram (Fig. 7) differs from the Fourier spectrogram is that cochlear travel-time delays morph the vertical glottal-pulse lines into curves. Another interesting difference is the increased emphasis of vowel onsets due to synaptic adaptation.

Two-Chamber and Three-chamber Tuning Curves

The two-chamber model includes SV and ST, so the only radial flow is BM velocity. Tectorial membrane (TM) motion is represented as a second mechanical degree-of-freedom that is coupled to BM motion through the reticular lamina (RL). The OHC HB motion is equal to the relative motion between TM and RL. OHC motility is modeled as an actuator that applies a force to the BM.

Figure 8. Hair-bundle iso-displacement tuning curves for a two-chamber, frequency-domain cochlear model at locations corresponding to characteristic frequencies at octave intervals from 0.25 to 16 kHz. The red circles are minimum-audible-pressure targets (Killion, 1978). The black dots indicate the best frequency at each location.

The three-chamber model includes SV, ST, and SS. The two radial flows are BM velocity and HB velocity, which is equal to the TM-RL relative velocity. As before, OHC motility is modeled as an actuator that applies a force on BM. A few additional model parameters are required to transition from two to three-chambers.

Figure 9. Hair-bundle iso-displacement tuning curves for a three-chamber, frequency-domain cochlear model.

The shapes of the two-chamber tuning curves differ from those of the three-chamber primarily in the distinct separation between their tip and tail sections. This separation is not a result of structural resonance but instead appears to be caused by a fluid-structure interaction. This mechanism may be fundamental to cochlear micromechanics and merits further investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

Here are the main points inferred from these cochlear-model results:

- Measurements in human ears of toneburst ABR latency and psychophysical forward masking provide constraints on models of human cochlear mechanics.
- Level dependence in measures of cochlear response is primarily due to a combination of
 1. OHC-transduction nonlinearity and
 2. synaptic-adaptation nonlinearity.
- Loudness increases due to stimulus-bandwidth increase (i.e., loudness summation) may provide indirect evidence of neural-ensemble averaging.
- Transmission-line models that have only a single radial DOF may provide inadequate representation of two DOF fluid interaction in cochlear micromechanics.
- A three-chamber fluid model, which allows a second radial DOF, exhibits transitions between the tips and tails of tuning curves that are more abrupt than have been observed in transmission-line models.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Dáibhid Ó Maoléidigh]: Does your model explain why loudness grows faster with level at low levels? Is there any other information in the literature about this faster growth and are there cochlear and central contributions?

[Stephen Neely]: In the present model, loudness grows faster at low levels because OHC mechano-electric transduction is more nearly linear. In other words, loudness grows more slowly at high levels due to increasing MET saturation.

Just-noticeable-differences in loudness are consistent with being due to variability in neural spike generation at IHC afferent synapses, so central contributions are probably minor (Allen and Neely 1997). The influence of cochlear-amplifier gain on loudness growth was explored in a previous MOH paper (Neely et al., 2000).

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[Karolina Charaziak]: Thank you for a great talk! Two questions: (1) Do you think that ABR wave V latency could be influenced by extracochlear factors such as pattern of innervation in CN, that has been hypothesized to "compensate" for TW delays? (2) Does your model predict differences in the loudness and perceived duration of so called "ramped" or "damped" sounds ([Grassi and Mioni 2020](#))?

[Stephen Neely]: (1) ABR wave V latency is used as a proxy for wave I latency because the I-V inter-wave latency is nearly constant across the range of stimulus levels where both waves are observable. Consequently, wave V latency appears to be mostly due to cochlear travel time; however, some CN compensation may also occur. (2) Thank-you for bringing to my attention that the differences in the loudness and perceived duration of so called "ramped" or "damped" sounds. These differences might be explained by forward masking due to IHC synaptic adaptation, which causes responses following abrupt onsets to be attenuated. This seems like an interesting modeling challenge.

[William Salloom]: Very interesting paper and work! I like how the paper covers both physiology and psychoacoustics to parametrize your model. I am curious how the critical band of loudness summation works with level dependence, and if you are or planning to incorporate that into your model since you are showing a clear level dependence with other parameters (i.e. cochlear latency and forward masking). In that case the cochlear filter bandwidths would increase as the level of the stimuli increases, but does that affect the overall loudness summation?

[Stephen Neely]: I do not have a good model of the critical band yet, but it does not appear to be solely determined by cochlear mechanics. I suspect that partial loudness judgements are made in CN based on neural ensemble averages and that each neural ensemble spans a region along the length of the cochlea equivalent to a critical band. This view allows for (1) the possibility of loudness reduction within a critical band for narrowband sounds and (2) the possibility of loudness summation across multiple critical bands for wideband sounds.